

ISic1492

Epitaph for Aisaris Sattaras

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

via S. Marta, fondo Martines

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory A3572

Physical Description

A rectangular slab of marble, heavily abraded on the upper right corner, but without obscuring the text.

Dimensions

Height 23 cm
Width 28.5 cm
Depth cm

Layout

Five lines of Greek, centred on the stone with an attempt to maintain regular margins. Guide lines are visible. Words are separated by substantial interpuncts, and the final line is visibly smaller.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Lines 1-4: 25 mm
Line 5: 15 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Θ(εοῖς) · Κ(αταχθονίοις) ·
2. Αἴσαρις · Σατ
3. τάρας · ἔζη
4. σεῦ · ἔτη
5. · ν · β ·

Apparatus

Translation (en)

To the underworld deities, Aisarīs Sataras lived for 52 years

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493876

EDCS 38200027

PHI 313673

Bibliography

Bitto, I. 2001. Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Messina. *Pelorias* 7. Messina. At 41

Ferrua, A 1941. *Analecta sicula. Epigraphica*. 3: 252-270. At 252-253 no.1

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